

Deliverable 5.1 - Reference catalogue of network reconstruction methods

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1 Version History

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2 Executive summary

The main computational goals of WP5 for Advances in Systems Ecology are to develop cutting edge network analysis methods, to define an all-Atlantic interactome and ecological niches, and to provide indicators of ecosystem stability and sensitivity to environmental stressors and drivers. Here, we reviewed the literature for ecological network reconstruction methods from several disciplines (microbiology, ecology, bioinformatics). We built a computational pipeline for the inference of species ecological networks from heterogeneous data types, combining statistical and ecological metrics, as well as probabilistic and machine learning algorithms. Reference databases of known ecological interactions obtained from the literature can be used to benchmark and validate inferred networks. This review of network inference algorithms is accompanied by a computational workflow: **AtlantEcoNet** (publicly available at: <https://gitlab.univ-nantes.fr/mbudinich/atlanteconet>), which builds upon existing software by integrating a selection of complementary methods for ecological network inference, analysis, and validation. This workflow will be used in Task 5.2 to build an all-Atlantic plankton ecological network from omics data compiled within WP2.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

Marine plankton and associated processes are at the core of global biogeochemical cycles, shaping ecosystem structure and influencing climate regulation (1). While global biodiversity maps for viruses, prokaryotes and microbial eukaryotes are beginning to emerge (2-4), identifying and understanding the complex network of interactions between these organisms and their environment is in its infancy (5). These interactions are critical to establish the ecosystem trophic links that underpin biogeochemical cycles and feedbacks that drive climate regulation and response (6, 7). While abiotic factors, such as temperature, can explain a large fraction of microbial community composition in the global ocean (8), biotic interactions can differentially shape ecosystem diversity (9), and can even influence the adaptation to new environments (10). Thus, determining how plankton ecological interactions are structured and affected by environmental change remains a significant challenge.

Large-scale holistic marine ecosystem sampling facilitates conceptualization of plankton community interactomes as co-occurrence networks that are useful to model the complex community structure of ecological associations (11, 12). Such networks have enabled the detection of communities assembled through niche overlap across biomes (13), and also the prediction of putative interactions such as parasitism or symbioses (14). Likewise, plankton co-occurrence networks have been instrumental in detecting interrelated changes in community structure from surface to depth (15), as well as to identify specific communities of key lineages (e.g. *Synechococcus*, its phages, and Collodaria) associated with global open ocean processes such as carbon export (16). Community interactomes are also useful to identify central, highly connected lineages that may play significant ecological roles and confer stability to the community (17). These central lineages can correspond to keystone taxa that are good indicators of community shifts (18). Understanding the mechanisms affecting these central taxa may help us to predict responses of microbiome structure and functioning to perturbations (19).

While community interactomes inferred from global-scale samplings summarize well the complexity and potential interactions within microbial assemblages (12), they usually do not reflect dynamic processes shaping the observed system, as measured by longitudinal high-frequency sampling (20). Nevertheless, plankton network metrics can capture emergent properties (e.g. connectivity) relating to ecological characteristics of the community (21), which can serve as proxies of ecosystem and community-level resilience (22). Given that biotic interactions can influence species distributions at macroecological scales (23), and that climate change may cause trophic cascading effects on plankton community structure by directly impacting the top and bottom of marine food webs (24), ecological interactions need to be considered for assessing plankton community stability under climate change scenarios.

Here, we reviewed the recent literature for ecological network reconstruction methods from sequencing data. We describe the various tasks from data filtering to normalization, to network inference, up to methods for validating inferred ecological networks. In addition, we built upon an existing computational package for the inference of ecological networks from heterogeneous data types, including omics, by combining statistical and ecological metrics, as well as probabilistic and machine learning algorithms. We complemented it by complementary methods for network inference, and by a new module for the automated validation of inferred associations using experiments and literature knowledge.

4 Inferring community networks

Inferring microbial association networks or community networks from high-throughput sequencing data has become a common task to explore and analyse the structure of natural microbial communities across biomes (12). In the last two decades, several ecological concepts and theories that have originally been developed for macroscopic organisms, have been adapted and applied to microbes in various environments (25). With the rise of environmental genomics and the exponential accumulation of sequencing data, classical ecological questions including species (co)-occurrence and diversity have been addressed for microorganisms (26-29). While most of these studies have usually focused on a single environment, others have investigated the global partitioning and structuring of microbial lineages across all sampled biomes (13, 30). Biodiversity influences ecosystem functions and services (31, 32). As community structures and trophic networks are also linked to ecosystem functioning (33, 34), and as warming is predicted to alter community structure and ecosystem functioning (35), microbial community networks are essential abstractions to study, survey, and predict the effect of climate change on ecosystem functioning (36). Below we review and describe the computational methods and tools for the inference of microbial community networks.

4.1 Data filtering, normalization, and transformation

The inference of microbial association networks usually starts with a matrix ($N \times s$) of non-negative observations or reads counts of s species or Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) resulting from the sequencing of N biological samples. The sequencing depth differs from sample to sample, which thus conditions the compositional nature of the data: Sequencing data are always compositional data (CoDa). In addition, due to technical factors, sequencing count data are sparse, that is contain many zeros. Due to the compositional and sparse nature of sequencing count data, specific normalization and/or transformation procedures are required prior to inferring associations, but are also determined with regards to the association metrics used. Classically, correlation metrics have been used to infer associations between taxa, without taking into account the compositional nature of the data.

Due to the high dimensional nature of abundance matrices generated from sequencing data, it is common practice to filter out a certain set of taxa as a first data preparation step. This is usually done by applying a filter on the prevalence across samples, or by imposing a minimal abundance for a given taxa within a single sample, or all across samples.

The sparse nature of sequencing data (many zeros) challenges computational and statistical analyses as parametric as well as non-parametric models may become invalid for data with a large number of zeros (37). Fortunately, a variety of compositionally aware measures have been developed and are based on log-ratios, which have been proposed by Aitchison (38) as the basis for statistical analyses of compositional data as they are independent of the total sum of counts in each sample. However, log-ratios cannot be computed if the count matrix contains any zeros, making zero handling necessary using replacement strategies (39, 40), such as adding pseudo counts that are usually below the minimum value reported in the abundance matrix.

Normalization techniques are required to make read counts comparable across different samples [47, 48]. As of today, the most commonly used approach consists in normalizing read counts of each sample to a unique sum, which is usually refer to as Total Sum Scaling (TSS). It is important to realize that this procedure does not change the compositional nature of the abundance data. Rather, proportions are always compositional, and actually even if the original data are not. Aitchison (38) suggested using the centered-log-ratio (clr) transformation to move compositional data from the simplex to real space. Alternative approaches consist in modelling the distribution of sequencing counts data in order to stabilize the associated variance using variance-stabilizing transformations (41). This has been proposed using the negative binomial distribution, and implemented in the commonly used DESeq2 (42) and edgeR (43) R packages.

Most commonly used data normalization techniques (also available in the *AtlantEcoNet* package) are the following:

- **Total sum scaling (TSS):** Traditional approach for building fractions. Counts are divided by the total sum of counts in the corresponding sample.
- **Cumulative sum scaling (CSS):** Within each sample, the counts are summed up to a predefined quantile. The counts are then divided by this sum.
- **Rarefaction:** Subsampling from the data to obtain samples with equal library size (also called rarefaction level)
- **Centered log-ratio (clr) transformation:** For a composition $x=(x_1,\dots,x_p)$ the clr transformation is defined as $\text{clr}(x)=\log(x_1/g(x),\dots,x_p/g(x))$, where $g(x)=(\prod_{k=1}^p x_k)^{1/p}$ is the geometric mean.
- **Variance stabilizing transformation (VST):** The dispersion-mean relation is fitted based on the count matrix. The data are then transformed to receive a matrix that is approximately homoscedastic.

4.2 Inferring associations

Once the data have been normalized and/or transformed, the following step is to estimate or quantify the association between taxa. Commonly used metrics to estimate associations are correlations, proportionality, and conditional dependence, for which computational methods and workflows (described in section 4.3) have been developed.

4.2.1 Correlation-based metrics

Classical approaches to infer ecological relationships have used presence-absence observations to infer co-occurrences or mutual exclusions (44), and interpreted these predictions as beneficial or competitive relations, respectively. With the availability of semi-quantitative information from sequencing data, methods have moved towards correlations metrics to measure associations between taxa (45), corresponding to co-abundances or compositional exclusions. Traditional correlation measures are the Pearson correlation, Spearman's rank correlation, as well as the biweight midcorrelation (bicor). While these metrics have been widely used, applying traditional correlation measures such as Pearson's correlation coefficient to compositions can lead to spurious negative correlations, which do not reflect underlying biological relationships (46).

In response, compositionally-aware correlation estimators have been developed, including SparCC (Sparse Correlations for Compositional data) (46), CCLasso (Correlation inference for Compositional data through Lasso) (47), and CCREPE (Compositionality Corrected by REnormalization and PErmutation) (45). SparCC is one of the first approaches developed for inferring correlations for compositional data and has become a widely used method. CCLasso is also based on log-ratios but aims to avoid the disadvantages of SparCC by using a latent variable model to infer a positive definite correlation matrix directly. The CCREPE approach operates directly on relative read counts, which are permuted and renormalized in order to detect correlations induced by compositionality alone. An alternative approach to reduce compositional effects is to normalize or transform the data in a compositionally aware manner and apply standard correlation coefficients to the transformed data. A common method is the clr transformation, which has now been implemented in state-of-the-art tools for microbial network inference such as FlashWeave (48) and NetCoMI (49).

4.2.2 Proportionality

Compositional data is widespread in life sciences and correlation metrics are still widely used to analyse and interpret pairwise relationships among biological entities. However, recent work has demonstrated that correlation is an inappropriate measure of associations for relative abundance data (50). Proportionality is proposed as an alternative association measure for compositional data: If two relative abundances are proportional, then their corresponding absolute abundances are proportional as well. Thus, proportionality is identical for the observed (relative) read counts and the true unobserved counts. Proportionality is measured based on the log-ratio variance. This variance, however, lacks a scale that would make the strength of association comparable. For this reason, dedicated proportionality measures ϕ and ρ , which are modifications

of the log-ratio variance based on clr transformed data that come with a scale, have been proposed and implemented in the Propr R package (51).

4.2.3 Conditional dependence

Conditional dependence expresses the relation between two variables conditioned on all other variables (52). Hence, this is a measure of direct relations between two given taxa, whereas (marginal) correlations cannot differentiate between direct and indirect dependencies. Several estimators of conditional dependence have recently been developed and all use graphical models to infer the conditional independence structure from the data. These estimators of conditional dependence are included in the package NetCoMi (49): SPRING (Semi-Parametric Rank-based approach for INference in Graphical model) (53), SPIEC-EASI (Sparse Inverse Covariance Estimation for Ecological Association Inference) (52) and gCoda (54). All these approaches presume that the assumptions of the data generation process are fulfilled for estimating a conditional dependence graph, so that its structure can be reliably inferred from the count matrix.

4.3 Computational methods and workflows

This section references and briefly describes current state-of-the-art computational methods and workflows for the compositionally aware inference of microbial association networks from (sequencing-based) spatial abundance data. Other statistical and computational methods dedicated to infer associations from longitudinal (time-series) data exist but are not considered nor discussed herein.

- CCREPE (45) works on relative abundances and performs statistical tests of significance of the estimated correlations, whereby spurious correlations caused by compositional effects are considered. The approach consists in permuting and re-normalizing the data to assess correlations due to compositionality alone. CCREPE is available as a R package: <https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/ccrepe.html>
- SparCC (46) estimates Pearson correlations from log-ratio variances via an approximation based on the assumption that taxa are uncorrelated on average. Zeros are handled using a Bayesian approach (observations replaced by random samples). SparCC is available as an R package: <https://github.com/MPBA/r-sparcc>
- CCLasso (47) infers correlations from observed counts via a latent variable model, which minimizes a loss function (considers errors resulting from estimating the covariance matrix from observed data instead of true abundances) plus a penalty to incorporate the sparsity assumption. CCLasso is implemented in R and available at: <https://github.com/huayingfang/CCLasso>
- Proportionality (50) relies on the fact that if two relative abundances are proportional, then their corresponding absolute abundances are proportional as well. Proportionality measures are modifications of the log-ratio variance based on clr transformed data that come with a scale. Proportionality metrics are implemented in the Propr R package available at: <https://github.com/tpq/propr>
- SPIEC-EASI (52) assumes a sparse underlying network and that the covariance matrix for clr-transformed data is approximately equal to the “true” covariance matrix. A graphical model is used to infer the conditional dependence structure between each two taxa. Two methods are available for graphical model inference: sparse inverse covariance selection and neighborhood selection. SPIEC-EASI is available as a R package: <https://github.com/zdk123/SpiecEasi>

- **SPRING** (53) estimates conditional independence relationships from the covariance matrix using neighborhood selection. The selection of the graphical model is performed via a stability-based approach.
SPRING is available as a R package: <https://github.com/GraceYoon/SPRING>
- **gCoda** (54) works on relative abundances and assumes that true absolute abundances follow a multivariate normal distribution, and a sparse underlying network. Conditional dependence relationships between taxa are determined by minimizing the negative log-Likelihood plus l1 penalty (to satisfy sparsity assumption) through an optimization problem solved via a Majorization- Minimization algorithm.
gCoda is implemented in R and available at: <https://github.com/huayingfang/gCoda>
- **FlashWeave** (48) relies on the Local-to-Global learning framework and infers direct associations by searching for conditional dependencies between taxa. Several heuristics are then applied to connect these “local” dependencies and infer a network. FW is significantly faster than other methods while achieving better or similar results, and gives the possibility to include meta-variables or contextual factors (such as the temperature).
FlashWeave is implemented in Julia and available at: <https://github.com/meringlab/FlashWeave.jl>

4.4 AtlantEcoNet (software package)

All the methods described above are available in the NetCoMi (49) R package, on top of which we built and developed the *AtlantEcoNet* R package. *AtlantEcoNet* add significant functionalities by integrating the *FlashWeave* algorithm (48), as well as a novel module (described below) to compare and validate inferred microbial associations with known associations stored in the Global Biotic Interactions (GloBI) database (55). *AtlantEcoNet* is publicly available at <https://gitlab.univ-nantes.fr/mbudinich/atlanteconet>.

5 Validating community networks

5.1 *In silico* validation

Different graph null models can be generated and used for validation purposes. Two R packages (*picante* v1.7 and *HMP* v1.6) are particularly useful to generate different types of graph null models. The *HMP* library (56) provides the *Dirichlet.multinomial* function, which allows data matrix generation of OTUs following a Dirichlet distribution. The *picante* package (57) comes with a *randomizeMatrix* function and several methods to randomize a given abundance or occurrence matrix. Different approaches, such as the *frequency* (maintaining OTUs occurrence frequency), and *trialswap* (maintaining OTUs occurrence frequency and sample OTUs richness) can be performed. Then, networks inferred from these matrices can be used to estimate a False Discovery Rate (FDR) by comparing common edges between observed and simulated networks.

5.2 Literature-based validation

The vast majority of ecological A number of databases collecting and serving known ecological interactions are available and can be used to validate empirical ecological networks inferred from *in situ* environmental data. The Global Biotic Interactions (GloBI) database (55) is likely the most comprehensive and generalist resource cataloguing biotic interactions across a wide range of organisms (<https://www.globalbioticinteractions.org/>). It provides open access and searchable species interaction data (e.g., predator-prey, pollinator-plant, pathogen-host, parasite-host) by combining existing open datasets and literature information using open-source software. More specialized databases also exist, in particular those dedicated to catalogue known interactions within the planktonic world. *AquaSymbio* is an expert manually-curated database listing symbiotic interactions (e.g., mutualistic, parasitic) such as endosymbiosis and parasitic relationships in aquatic ecosystems

(<http://aquasymbio.fr>). These known interactions are often supported imaging and characterized in associated publications. Other resources also list known interactions manually extracted from the literature, such as the Protist Interaction database PIDA (58) that collect interactions determined by direct observations (e.g., light microscopy, SEM) and/or by molecular methods (e.g., sequencing, FISH) (<https://github.com/ramalok/PIDA>). More specific databases have also been constructed such as the Diatom Interaction DataBase (DIDB) dedicated to list all ecological interactions involving diatoms in the literature (<https://github.com/FloraVincent/DIDB>). These resources are scarce and far from being complete, as ecological interactions in nature are difficult to detect, characterize, and validate. Nevertheless, they assemble information that are particularly useful to benchmark and compare the performance and sensitivity of ecological network inference methods. Indeed, known interactions can searched in inferred ecological networks by detecting all associations of OTUs at various taxonomic levels. This approach allows to estimate precision and recall of predictions by computing true and false positives as well as false negatives. Thus, using this approach, we implemented and integrated a literature-based validation module within the AtlantEcoNet package. This R module (https://gitlab.univ-nantes.fr/mbudinich/atlantconet/-/blob/master/R/globi_validation.R) uses the GloBI database as a gold standard reference for known interactions and allows the automated search and validation of known interactions in generated or provided networks.

5.3 Experimental validation

Community association networks constitute useful resources providing putative key ecological associations among often mostly uncultivated plankton taxa identified at the molecular level. Still, these networks are limited because predicted ecological associations do not demonstrate ecological interactions (59), and because it does not capture the dynamics of plankton interactions that are usually assessed using temporal or longitudinal samplings (60). Our knowledge of plankton microbiomes, symbioses, and host-parasite relationships remains limited (58). While *in silico* predictions are useful to further our understanding of ecosystem functioning, planktonic interactions need to be validated using classical and novel high-throughput experimental techniques.

5.3.1 Single-cell omics validation

Integrating imaging and molecular data can reveal novel interactions occurring in the environment. Guided by *in silico* predictions of associations, acoel flatworms (*Symsagittifera* sp.) together with their photosynthetic green microalgal endosymbionts (*Tetraselmis* sp.) were collected in microplankton samples from a Tara Oceans sample in the Mediterranean Sea, imaged and taxonomically identified (14). Conversely, imaging data can reveal intriguing associations and guide the sequencing of *de novo* isolated cells from existing samples. For example, an epibiotic association between the diatom *Fragilariopsis doliolus* and genera of tintinnid ciliates were first observed in Tara Oceans stations from the South Atlantic Ocean (61). In this study, after initial isolation and molecular identification, the distribution of both partners was recovered and guided the choice of stations at which to perform further imaging and in depth ribotyping. The study revealed that *F. doliolus*, one of the most abundant diatoms in the global ocean, forms unique barrel-shaped chains that enable interactions with tintinnids. The consortia were particularly prevalent in nutrient-replete conditions, which are rich in potential predators, supporting the hypothesis of a mutualistic symbiosis wherein diatoms acquire motility and tintinnids benefit from the armour-like protection of the diatom's silicified barrel. Another study, combining single consortia isolation, imaging, and sequencing, revealed that the photosynthetic dinoflagellate genus *Symbiodinium* establish mutualistic endosymbioses with a wide diversity of benthic hosts. These studies reveal the power of combining imaging, single-cell isolation, and sequencing to identify, and at the same time validate, novel planktonic interactions in the environment. A number of single cells have actually been isolated from promising Tara Oceans samples with the goal to sequence and identify both eukaryotic hosts and putative prokaryotic symbionts through amplification and sequencing of both 16S and 18S rRNA genes. This approach has the potential to reveal novel important symbioses supporting key biogeochemical and ecosystem services within the plankton biome.

5.3.2 Experiments in the lab and at sea

Today, high-throughput co-culture experiments using microfluidics (62) and fabricated synthetic microbial ecosystems may help fill our knowledge gap of plankton community interactions (63). An all Atlantic interactome (Task 5.2) will constitute useful guidance for co-culture experiments, as well as a database for hypothesis testing. In addition, *in situ* experiments on board AtlantECO flagship cruises and in aquaculture facilities will produce valuable information to validate our network predictions and analyses planned in Task 5.2.

6 Conclusion

The goal of Task 5.1 of WP5 for Advances in Systems Ecology was to review and improve statistical and computational methods for ecological network reconstruction. And also, to build a computational pipeline combining selected computational methods to generate species ecological networks (i.e. interactomes) from heterogeneous data types. Here, we reviewed network reconstruction methods recently developed, in particular methods taking into account the compositional nature of sequencing-derived molecular data. We described the essential pre-processing tasks prior to compute microbial associations and described a selection of state-of-the-art computational methods for the task. We developed and implemented the *AtlantEcoNet* package by building upon a recently developed R package including these methods (NetCoMi), which was complemented by a novel machine learning-based algorithm (FlashWeave). The latter algorithm was extensively tested and benchmarked against other state-of-the-art methods using the most comprehensive reference database of known microbiome ecological interactions obtained from the literature (GloBI) (36). In addition, *AtlantEcoNet* implements an original method to estimate accuracy of microbial association predictions by identifying previously known interactions. Thus, *AtlantEcoNet* will be instrumental in successfully achieving Task 5.2 that will consist in constructing cross-kingdom association networks for microbiome and plastisphere communities from the all-Atlantic data assembled in WP2.

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